

eXtreme Design for Digital Humanities – Tilting at Ontological Windmills with Patterns and Principles?

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Introduction

Ontologies and knowledge graphs (KGs) have become irreplaceable instruments in the toolkit of digital humanities (DH) research. They offer ways to represent and interconnect a myriad of heterogeneous resources in a standardized, structured manner.

This workshop aims to both foster the use of ontologies in the DH and address recurring challenges in DH ontology engineering, proposing improvements with eXtreme design (XD) as a fundamental principle for future semantic technology endeavors. XD is a dynamic, iterative approach that focuses on modularization and the (re)use of ontology design patterns (ODPs) [1-6]. It represents a systematic approach for the development of distinctive architectures for knowledge representations.

Participants will be confronted with questions regarding the creation and use of ontologies and recurring challenges and pitfalls in ontologies and ontology engineering. Through use cases, the workshop aims to simulate an ontology engineering process with XD and motivate participants to critically evaluate the workflow and the resulting ontologies.

Semantic Technologies in the DH: A Two-Edged Sword

The DH comprise different disciplines, thus combining various heterogeneous data resources, research questions, multiple perspectives, and methodologies. Accurate data models are the baseline for drawing correlations between these resources and across disciplines – a core principle of humanities research. Additionally, the DH are dynamic, depending on ever-evolving technologies, the need to understand their impact on humanities research and, most importantly, on the significance of interpretation and meaning-making [7].

KGs bring solutions for this, making it possible to encode multidisciplinary data, capture multiple perspectives and interpretations of the same data, and to interconnect decentralized resources. Ontologies are the heart of a KG, defining what kind of knowledge it contains. This is a collection of well-defined definitions of concepts, entities, and their relationships for a specific domain. In combined force, ontologies and KGs offer rich, flexible models for representing complex knowledge in a human- and machine-understandable way. Knowledge can be queried and connected with external resources, logical axioms making it possible to infer additional information. Optimally, these models can be adapted to change, ensuring that they remain relevant over time [8–11].

In an ideal world, this allows for the integration of diverse resources and cross-disciplinary exploration. However, in reality, multiple – often incompatible – standards share the stage with heterogeneous data resources. In DH ontology engineering, the reuse of existing ontologies like CIDOC or FRBR is already common practice. Nevertheless, the aforementioned characteristics of DH data often require even more specialized concepts. As a solution, many applications construct complex representations of their use case specific perspectives on the data. This reduces interoperability between projects due to non-standardized models. Future interlinking of related facts across datasets becomes difficult. Additionally, in such cases, the ontologies are often developed regardless of feedback from actual users of the end product, obstructing the way they serve real-world requirements in the long run. Accordingly, many ontologies are hardly re-used outside of the use cases they were designed for [4, 17; 18]

This issue underscores the importance of open and FAIR research principles in DH [12, 13]. Their adoption in ontology engineering shows a commitment to the importance of collaboration and knowledge transfer across various DH applications.

eXtreme Design and Ontology Design Patterns

The XD methodology is a dynamic, user-centered approach to ontology engineering. It consists of four core workflow phases: requirements analysis, design and development, testing, and release. In focus are rigorous documentation of all engineering steps, the high involvement of domain experts who bridge the gap between developers and end users, and the reuse or creation of ODPs. ODPs are modeling solutions for recurring design problems in ontologies. They function like building blocks, providing a common foundation for ontology modules and help to keep solutions sectioned, providing small and modular frameworks for particular use cases. Developed patterns are shared with the community in dedicated repositories and can be imported, specialized, and composed. It is also possible to extract ODPs from existing ontologies.

While XD has benefitted related domains such as cultural heritage or other fields like material sciences, it has yet to establish itself as a standard practice in the DH ontology engineering toolbox (see the ArCo KG, Polifonia, DigiKar, MatWerk, ...) [14–16]. However, XD addresses several of the previously pointed out challenges: to overcome inaccurate or over complex knowledge representations, domain experts can provide in-depth understanding of the specific domain and reflect realistic requirements. Documented artifacts from the requirements analysis make it possible to trace the decision making and are used for evaluating the ontology. Combined with modularization, the iterative development fosters the possibility of continuous refinement, making it easier to maintain and adapt only small parts instead of an exhaustive data model. To address the disparity between reuse of existing ontologies and creating use case specific ontologies, ODPs and mappings to upper ontologies can be used. Adopting ODPs allows for ontologies development like the construction of (toy) brick houses, for which ODPs then function like interconnectable building blocks. This allows for knowledge transferability, even across domains.

Objectives

This workshop aims to equip DH scholars with XD as a tool for creating better, FAIRer ontologies. XD addresses the aforementioned challenges in the application of semantic technologies to DH data, combining a user-centered approach with dedicated, pattern-based modeling.

During the workshop, the participants will learn more about the introduced challenges and assess their impact on ontologies and KGs in the DH. A first session will introduce ontologies, their creation and potential pitfalls, then XD as a possible solution. In order to emphasize the utility of XD for the DH, all participants will walk through the different core workflow phases, including requirements analysis, design, testing, and release.

The workshop aims to simulate real-world DH projects and applied engineering processes in a practical setting. Participants of the workshop will be divided into smaller groups for different DH project simulations, each group receiving an exemplary (fictional) DH-specific modeling task and a corresponding research question.

Throughout the sessions, the attendees will try to answer questions such as: How can we consult with domain experts? How can we ensure that the conceptualizations within the ontology reflect realistic nuances and complexities given in the domain? In what way can we properly document all steps? How can we model FAIR knowledge representations for scenarios in the DH?

The workshop exemplifies the functionality of ODPs in particular by encouraging participants to reuse existing patterns in the engineering process. With the provided datasets, the workshop intends to breach the discipline's boundaries, fostering interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and collaboration. In a final discussion session, the solutions will be presented to the entire workshop and the different research questions debated in plenum.

Researchers and Interests

Sarah Rebecca Ondraszek: PhD student in Computer Science in the Information Service Engineering (ISE) group at FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur.

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Harald Sack: Head of the ISE group at FIZ, full professor at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Institute for Applied Informatics and Formal Description Methods (AIFB).

All researchers are working and contributing to one or more NFDI projects, including NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, and NFDI4MatWerk, with extensive knowledge in the intersection of semantic technologies and DH. Their focus is diverse, including the development of knowledge bases (e.g., Culture Portal and 4Memory Data Space), domain-relevant ontologies, and the use of eXtreme Design and Ontology Design Patterns in DH.

Target Audience, Format and Prerequisites

Appreciated but not required: A basic understanding of ontologies, KGs, RDF and SPARQL; familiarity with ontology design methods.

Workshop language: English.

Workshop length: Two days.

Necessary technical equipment: Participants should bring laptops; internet access, a projector.
Group size: max. 30 participants.

First day:

At the beginning of each phase, workshop leaders will give an example for the task and a detailed explanation of what participants need to do.

1. Introduction to ontologies, ontology engineering, challenges in the DH, XD as a possible solution (1 h).

2. Phase 1: Requirements Analysis (1 h)

- a. Domain and data analysis, simulated user interviews with domain experts for better understanding of domain-specific concepts.
- b. Documentation of all steps in personas, user stories, and competency questions.

3. Phase 2: Design and Development (2 h)

Based on the collected requirements and example given by the workshop leaders:

- a. Selection and adoption of existing patterns,
- b. OR development of new patterns.
- c. Implementation in Protégé.

Second day

4. Phase 3: Evaluation (2 h)

- a. Respective groups present their ontology.
- b. With competency questions from Phase 1, the presenting team and audience evaluate the ontologies.

5. Phase 4: Deployment: Future Steps and Discussion (2 h)

- a. Discussion of crucial aspects, including:
 - i. Deployment and documentation,
 - ii. Version control,
 - iii. Interoperability with existing DH infrastructures and mapping to upper ontologies,
 - iv. Reusability of developed ontology components.
- b. Remaining challenges, future perspectives.

References

- [1] E. F. Kendall, D. L. McGuinness, Foundations, in: *Ontology Engineering*, Springer International Publishing, 2019. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-79486-5_1.
- [2] A. Gómez-Pérez, M. Fernández-López, O. Corcho, Methodologies and Methods for Building Ontologies, in: *Ontological Engineering: With Examples from the Areas of Knowledge Management, e-Commerce and the Semantic Web*, Springer London, 2004. doi:10.1007/1-85233-840-7_3.
- [3] V. Presutti, et al., eXtreme design with content ontology design patterns, in: *Proceedings of the 2009 International Conference on Ontology Patterns*, Vol. 516 of WOP'09, CEURWS.org, 2009.
- [4] A. Gangemi, V. Presutti, Ontology Design Patterns, in: *Handbook on Ontologies*, 2009. doi:10.1007/978-3-540-92673-3_10.
- [5] V. Presutti, et al., Pattern-Based Ontology Design, in: *Ontology Engineering in a Networked World*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-24794-1_3.
- [6] E. Blomqvist, et al., Experimenting with eXtreme Design, in: *Knowledge Engineering and Management by the Masses*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2010. doi:10.3233/978-1-61499-676-7-23.
- [7] A. Meroño-Peñuela et al., “CLARIAH: Enabling Interoperability Between Humanities Disciplines with Ontologies,” in *Applications and Practices in Ontology Design, Extraction, and Reasoning*, 2020, pp. 73–90. doi: 10.3233/SSW200036.
- [8] A. Hogan et al., “Data Graphs,” in *Knowledge Graphs*, A. Hogan et al., Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 5–23. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-01918-0_2.
- [9] A. Hogan et al., “Introduction,” in *Knowledge Graphs*, A. Hogan et al., Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-01918-0_1.
- [10] A. Hogan et al., “Deductive Knowledge,” in *Knowledge Graphs*, A. Hogan et al., Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 47–65. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-01918-0_4.
- [11] A. Hogan et al., “Creation and Enrichment,” in *Knowledge Graphs*, A. Hogan et al., Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 105–117. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-01918-0_6.
- [12] M. D. Wilkinson et al., “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
- [13] D. Garijo and M. Poveda-Villalón, “Best Practices for Implementing FAIR Vocabularies and Ontologies on the Web.” 2020. doi: arXiv:2003.13084.
- [14] V. Carriero, et al., Pattern-based design applied to cultural heritage knowledge graphs, *Semantic Web* 12 (2) (2021). doi:10.3233/SW-200422.
- [15] A. M. Tirado, et al., Musical Meetups: a Knowledge Graph approach for Historical Social Network Analysis, in: *ESWC 2023 Workshops and Tutorials. Semantic Methods for Events and Stories (SEMMES)*, Vol. 3443, CEUR-WS.org, 2023. URL <https://oro.open.ac.uk/88720/>
- [16] G. Renda, M. Grasso, M. Daquino, From ontology design to user-centred interfaces for music heritage (2023). doi:10.48550/arXiv.2306.12973.
- [17] C. Shimizu, K. Hammar, and P. Hitzler, “Modular ontology modeling,” *Semantic Web*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 459–489, 2023, doi: 10.3233/SW-222886.
- [18] P. Hitzler, “A review of the semantic web field,” *Commun. ACM*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 76–83, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1145/3397512.